

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

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ABSTRACT: This descriptive research aims to examine the values education in a secondary school via teacher views. The data collection method of the research is mixed method as it includes both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. The study group of the research consists of teachers at a public secondary school in Aydın. Data were collected from 15 teachers by questionnaire and five teachers by interviews. Descriptive analysis such as percentage, frequency and mean of the obtained data were calculated. As for the findings; values education defines as social benefit and moral development. The influence of the parents on values education is more than the influence of media, peers, school or teacher. The type of TV program watched by students, the role model of teachers and the reason for using the internet have influence on the development of values. It has been concluded that the verbal weighted lessons are more effective in the development of the values of the students, and that the goals/acquisitions related to values education cannot be reached at the desired level.

KEYWORDS: Values education, teachers' view, descriptive

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been an increase in moral degradation, addictions, prejudices, violence, social problems and lack of respect among young people in almost all societies (UNESCO, 2005). These negative features contradict the values accepted by the society. Value is the whole of the material and moral elements that cover the social, cultural, economic and scientific values of a nation (TDK, 2023). Values education, on the other hand, was defined by Ekşi (2003) as an effort to help the new generation gain basic human values, create sensitivity to values and transform them into behavior. Battistich (2006; cited in Gökçek, 2007) explained the purpose of values education as raising good children who are understanding, caring, having moral values, productive, using their capacities to do the best in their youth, doing the right things, understanding the purpose of life and living accordingly. Girgin (2012) states that value expresses society's beliefs and attitudes.

Every society has its own values, and individuals adapt to society by realizing their social and emotional development with these values (Pahl & Barrett, 2007). Societies make great efforts to bring these values to individuals. The main way to achieve success on this path is through education (Altın & Altın, 2021). Bringing the values accepted by the society to individuals has been the aim of values education and has been one of the important subjects of education in recent years (Keskin, 2008). Schools are given the task of bringing values to students. Therefore, educational activities, curricula and textbooks used at schools are prepared by considering values education (Koç, 2013). Similarly, Ryan (1993) states that schools should be pioneers in bringing values to individuals so that values education studies carried out in schools are considered crucial. The aim of this research is to examine the values education at a secondary school in Aydın through the views of teachers. According to the main purpose of study, the sub-problems to be answered are given below;

1. What does values education mean?
2. What affects the values education?
3. How much is the values education realized at school?

II. METHOD

The study was designed as a descriptive study; because descriptive studies are research models that aim to explain a past or existing situation descriptively (Karasar, 2012). The model of the research is mixed method since it includes two types of data collection methods (quantitative & qualitative). The research applying mixed methods is a type of research in which the researcher or research team combines qualitative and quantitative research approach components (for example, the use of qualitative and quantitative perspectives, data collection, analysis and inference techniques) for the breadth and depth of understanding and validation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2015).

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

A. Study Group

The study group of the research consists of a public secondary school selected by simple random sampling method in Aydin province. Data were collected from 15 teachers working in the school by questionnaire and from five teachers by interviews. Personal information about the teachers participating in the research is given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Participants' personal information

		f	%		f	%		f	%		f	%
Gender	Female	7	46,7	Male	8	53,3						
Graduation	Bachelor	13	86,7	Master	2	13,3						
Age	20-30	5	33,3	31-40	8	53,3	41-50	2	13,3			
Seniority	0-5	3	20	6-10	6	40	11-15	3	20	16-20	3	20

Table 2. Branches of Teachers

Branch	n	%
Turkish teacher	3	20,0
Science teacher	3	20,0
Social studies teacher	2	13,3
Maths teacher	2	13,3
English teacher	2	13,3
Visual arts teacher	1	6,7
Religious culture and moral knowledge teacher	1	6,7
Phsyical education teacher	1	6,7

In addition, data were obtained through interviews with two mathematics teachers, one of whom has been teaching for six years and the other for nine years, an religious culture and moral knowledge teacher who has been teaching for two years, a visual arts teacher who has been teaching for 19 years, and a technology & design teacher who has been teaching for 10 years.

B. Data Collection and Analysis

In the study, the data were collected by the questionnaire and interview technique. The questionnaire and semi-structured questionnaire form was developed by the researcher. Percentage, frequency and rank average calculations were made for the analysis of the information obtained through the questionnaires. The data collected through interviews were analysed through content analysis technique.

III. FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The findings obtained from the research data are given in the order of the sub-problems.

A. Findings Related to First Sub-Problem

The first sub-problem of the research, "What does values education mean?" Findings related to the question are given in Table 3.

Table 3. The definitions for values education

Definitions	f	%
Social benefit	3	30
Moral development	2	20
Responsibility	1	10
Development of personality	1	10
Helpfulness	1	10
Tolerance	1	10
Formality studies	1	10

It has been seen at the Table 3 that three teachers (30%) state that values education will provide social benefits, and two teachers think that it means moral development in students (20%).

B. Findings Related to Second Sub-Problem

The second sub-problem of the research, "What is effective in students' values?" Findings related to the question are given in Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7.

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

Table 4. Ranking of factors having effects on values education

Factors	Place in ranking
Family	1,8
Media	2,78
Peer	2,92
School	3,21

From the questionnaire filled by the teachers, it was found that the family has the most affect ($x=1.8$) on the values education of the children. Family is followed by media (2.78), peers (2.92) and school (3.21) in the order of effective factors in values education. The interviews with the teachers also revealed that the effect of the family on values education is more than the other factors.

Table 5. The average ranking of effects of family characteristics on values education

Features	Ranking of importance
Family communicaiton	3,78
Faith and value	3,92
Family union	4,07
Education level	4,71
Socio-economics	5,85
Nuclear family	5,92
Residential area	6,69
Large family	6,92
Kinship communication	7,14

In the questionnaire filled by the teachers, family communication ($x=3.78$) took the first place in the order of importance of family characteristics affecting values education, followed by belief and value with an average of 3.92, being together with parents with an average of 4.07, Education level with an average of 4.71, socio-economic level with an average of 5.85, a nuclear family with an average of 5.92, where the family lives with an average of 6.69, and extended family with an average of 6.92 and kinship communication with an average of 7.14. Also, from the interviews with the teachers, it was found that the different characteristics of the family are effective in values education. Teachers did not focus on one feature.

Table 6. The order of the influence of the media in values education

Direction of impact	Order of importance
TV show	3,28
Clear purpose of use	3,35
Time on the net	4,21
TV duration	4,35
Magazine/newspaper followed	4,42
Magazine/newspaper qualification	4,71
Critical media literacy	5,42

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that TV programs rank first in the importance of the media in values education in the questionnaire filled out by teachers ($X=3,28$). This is followed by the purpose of using the internet with an average of 3.35, the time spent on the internet ($X=4.21$), the time spent in front of the TV ($X=4.35$), the follow-up of a periodical publication such as a magazine/newspaper ($X=4.42$), the quality of the periodicals (4.71) and critical media literacy ($X=5.42$). Interviews with teachers revealed similarities to the findings from the questionnaire.

Table 7. Order of importance of the influence of schools and teachers in values education

Aspect of the influence of schools and teachers	Order of importance
Teacher's love of profession	6,14
The nature of the teacher	6,28
Openness of the teacher to development	6,57
An environment for children to express themselves	6,57
Individual differences of students	6,69
School surroundings	6,92
Education at school	7,35
Facilities of the school	8,50

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

Qualifications of the school administrator	8,71
Extracurricular activities provided by the school	9,36
Teachers' economic level	9,64
Teachers' in-service training	10,07
Libraries and research opportunities	10,71
Infrastructure for sportive events	10,85
Private school	11,78
Public school	12,07
Variety of elective lessons	13,07

When Table 7 is examined, in the questionnaire filled out by the teachers, the teacher's love for his profession with an average of 6.14 is in the first place in terms of importance of the aspects of the school and teachers on values education. This is followed by the quality of the teacher ($X=6.28$), the teacher's openness ($x=6.57$), the teacher's openness to development ($x=6.57$), the individual difference of the learners ($x=6.69$), the school surroundings ($x=6.92$) and the education provided in the school ($x=7.35$). Via interviews realized with participants, it is founded that the role model of teachers is emphasized.

Table 8. Teachers' opinions on the influence of lessons on values education

Testimonials	f	%
Yes	7	58,3
Partly	3	25
No	2	16,7
Total	14	100

Table 8 shows that seven teachers (58.3%) stated that the lessons in the school are crucial in values education. From the interviews with the teachers, it was found that the lessons had an effect on values education.

Table 9. Ranking of lessons in terms of contributing to values education

Lessons	Order of contributions
Education of religion and ethics	2,45
Psychological counseling and guidance	2,5
Social studies	3,3
Turkish	5
Physical education and sports	5,33
Human rights	6,14
Music	7
Foreign language	7,42
Science	7,83
Life science	8,5
Technology & design	8,62
Visual arts	8,71
Mathematics	9,5

In the questionnaire filled out by the teachers, the first place in the ranking of the courses in terms of contributing to values education is the verbal weighted courses like Education of religion and ethics course ($X=2.45$), Psychological counseling and guidance ($X=2.5$), Social Studies ($X=3.3$) and Turkish ($X=5$), while the last place is the Mathematics course with an average of 9.5. Similar findings were obtained from interviews with teachers.

C. Findings Related to Second Sub-Problem

The findings of the third sub-problem of the research, "How much is the values education realized at school?" are given in Tables 10 and 11.

Table 10. Teachers' views on the achievement of goals related to values education

Testimonials	f	%
Agree	6	42,9
I partially agree	3	21,4
Disagree	3	21,4
I disagree at all	2	14,3
Total	14	100

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

Table 10 shows teachers' opinions whether the goals related to values education are achieved. From the table, it is understood that teachers mostly agree with this view (agree f=6 [42.9%] and partially agree f=3 [21.4%]). However, from the interviews with the teachers, it was found that the goals related to values education were not achieved.

Findings about degree of importance and realization of goals in values education have not been adequately achieved are also included in the table of the importance of values and the degree of realization.

Table 11. The degree of importance of values and the degree of realization of values at schools

Values	Importance									Degree of realization										
	A lot		Enough		A little		Too little		Never		A lot		Enough		A little		Too little		Never	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Honesty	12	92,3			1	7,7					1	7,7	1	7,7	7	53,8	3	23,1	1	7,7
Traditionalism	5	38,5	6	46,2	1	7,7	1	7,7			4	30,8	2	15,4	4	30,8	3	23,1		
Empathy/compassion	11	84,6	1	7,7	1	7,7						1	7,7	5	33,3	5	33,3	2	13,3	
Fairness	11	73,3	1	7,7	1	7,7						1	7,7	5	33,3	7	53,8			
Self-esteem	11	86,7	1	7,7			1	7,7						5	33,3	7	53,8	1	7,7	
Democratic thinking	11	91,7					1	8,3						3	25	9	75			
Virtuousness/virtue	12	92,3			1	7,7						1	7,7	5	33,3	6	46,2	1	7,7	
Self-control/discipline	12	92,3							1	7,7				2	13,3	8	53,3	3	23,1	
Sportsmanship	6	46,2	6	46,2	1	7,7								6	46,2	6	46,2	1	7,7	
Having love	12	92,3			1	7,7						1	7,7	9	69,2	3	23,1			
Courage	10	76,9	3	23,1							3	23,1	3	23,1	4	30,8	3	23,1		
Follow the rules	12	92,3			2	7,7								2	15,4	9	69,2	2	15,4	
Respect for human rights	12	92,3					1	7,7						2	16,7	8	66,7	2	16,7	
Pride	5	41,7	1	8,3	3	25	1	8,3	2	13,3	3	23,1	3	23,1	3	23,1	4	30,8		
Humility/Humility	11	84,6	1	7,7			1	7,7						6	46,2	6	46,2	1	7,7	
Honor	10	83,3	1	8,3			1	8,3				1	7,7	7	53,8	4	30,8	1	7,7	
Loyalty/loyalty/devotion	11	73,3	1	7,7	1	7,7					1	8,3		6	50	4	33,3	1	8,3	
Social responsibility	11	84,6	1	7,7			1	7,7						2	15,4	1	66,7	1	7,7	
Generosity	11	84,6	1	7,7	1	7,7						1	8,3	5	41,7	5	41,7	1	8,3	
Share	10	76,9	2	15,4	1	7,7						1	8,3	5	41,7	5	41,7	1	8,3	
Piety	8	61,5	3	23,1	2	15,4					2	15,4	3	23,1	5	38,5	3	23,1		
Frugality	7	53,8	3	23,1	2	15,4	1	7,7			1	7,7	1	7,7	6	46,2	5	38,5		
Mindfulness	10	76,9	2	15,4	1	7,7						1	7,7	6	46,2	5	38,5	1	7,7	
Patience	11	84,6	1	7,7	1	7,7								4	30,8	2	46,2	3	23,1	

The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

Politeness/kindness	11	84,6	1	7,7			1	7,7				1	7,7	2	15,4	6	46,2	4	30,8	
Optimism	12	92,3					1	7,7				2	15,4	5	38,5	5	38,5	1	7,7	
Competitiveness	7	58,3	1	8,3	3	25	1	8,3				4	30,8	5	38,5	3	23,1	1	7,7	
Cooperation/teamwork spirit	10	76,9			2	15,4	1	7,7			1	7,7	2	15,4	3	23,1	6	46,2	1	7,7
Wisdom/wisdom	10	76,9	1	7,7	1	7,7			1	7,7		1	7,7	3	23,1	6	46,2	3	23,1	
Hospitality	9	69,2	2	13,3	2	13,3					4	30,8	1	7,7	4	30,8	3	23,1	1	7,7

When Table 11 is examined, the importance of the values and the level of realization of these values in school are given in the questionnaire filled out by the teachers. Accordingly, while most of the values are considered very important, most of them are realized a little or very little. For example while honesty was considered very important (92.3%), it was realized a little at school (53.8%). Similarly, while democratic thinking is considered crucial (91.7%), it occurs too little in school (75%). According to the Table 11, while most of the values are seen very important, it can be said that the level of measure of realization of the values isn't sufficient.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research, which was conducted to examine the values education activities in a secondary school through the opinions of the teachers, were given according to the order in the sub-problem.

Values education is defined by several words, such as social benefit or moral development. Values education is defined with similar words in the study of Aydın and Akyol Güler (2014). Also, Yeşil and Aydın (2007) argue values education as social education for making the individuals to behave as the society approves.

The effect of the family on values education is greater than the effects of other factors (media, peer, school and teacher). Gündoğdu, Üstündağ Kocakuşığı, Altın, Eken, Yolcu and Çırakoğlu (2019) also emphasized the impact of the family on values education. The type of TV program watched and the reason for using the internet have influences on the development of values. Tomlinson (2004) also emphasized the impact of the media on values in his study. Teachers as role model have effects on the students' values. Avcı (2011) founded that teachers as role models have effects on the students' values. Uysal (2007) argued that as parents and society couldn't give sufficient values education, educators as teachers and educational institutes as school are considered responsible for values education. Moreover, verbal-weighted lessons as a social sciences are more effective in values education.

While the goals for values education are considered very important, the goals aren't achieved at the desired rate. Ateş (2013) stated that values education practices in the education system were insufficient.

Based on the results of the research, some suggestions can be made. The influence of the family on values education could be searched via interviews with family members. Implementations of values education in verbal-weighted lessons can be examined through observation and interviews with branch teachers. Teachers of quantitative-weighted courses should pay more attention to values education. Experimental studies should be emphasized in order to achieve the goals/achievements related to values education. Teachers should be given in-service training courses related to values education.

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The Examination of the Values Education through Teachers' Views: Sample of a Secondary School

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